

Theoretical study of crystalline state properties of heavy metal halide with different structures

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Abstract : The crystalline state properties such as cohesive energy, atomization energy, force constant, IR absorption frequency, Debye temperature, Grüneisen parameter, Anderson Grüneisen parameter, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter of heavy metal halide are reported here. These parameters have been obtained by using the Born-Mayer, Hellmann, Varshini-Shukla and Ali-Hasan interionic short-range repulsive interactions. Calculations are also performed for the computation of first order volume dependence of Grüneisen parameter commonly known as second Grüneisen parameter using expressions of higher order derivatives of interaction potential within the framework of Dugdale and MacDonald theory. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals has also been studied.

Keywords : Crystalline state properties, Grüneisen parameter, second Grüneisen parameter.

Introduction

The nature of bonding in ionic crystals has been the centre of attraction for theoretical as well as experimental physicists and chemists as it plays a vital role in solid state physics. Several attempts have been made to understand the nature of interaction between the atoms of an ionic crystal and hence to decide the form of interaction potential for such a crystal. Once the reliable form of interaction potential is known, it is possible to study the crystalline state properties of heavy metal halide crystals. The crystal state properties of heavy metal halide have been studied by several workers. But these investigators employed the interaction models¹⁻⁴ with repulsive parts that are either inverse power functions or exponential functions or phenomenological in nature. But none of these are capable enough of explaining all the observed macroscopic properties of diatomic crystals. The search for the interaction potential function satisfying the essential requirements of ideal potential function⁵ continues.

In the present paper we have used the Born-Mayer⁶, Hellmann⁷, Varshini-Shukla⁸ and Ali-Hasan⁹ short-range repulsive potential to evaluate the crystalline state properties of heavy metal halide crystals. The reason for selecting these models lies in their suitability of evaluating their state properties as well as molecular state properties. Moreover, these potentials fulfil the fundamental physical requirements of an ideal potential.

Method of analysis :

Crystal energy : The crystal lattice energy per ion

pair can be expressed as

$$\Phi(r) = \Phi_e + \Phi_v + \Phi_{SR} \quad (1)$$

Here Φ_e is the long-range electrostatic coulomb energy with Madelung constant A . It is given by

$$\Phi_e = -Az_1 z_2 e^2/r \quad (2)$$

where $z_1 e$ and $z_2 e$ are the electrostatic charges on the ion pairs and r is the interionic separation.

The second term, Φ_v , on the R.H.S. of the eq. (1) represents the van der Waals energy expressed as

$$\Phi_v = -C/r^6 - D/r^8 \quad (3)$$

where C and D are van der Waals (vdw) dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients and are given by

$$C = S_{+-} c_{+-} + S_{++} c_{++} + S_{--} c_{--} \\ \text{and } D = T_{+-} d_{+-} + T_{++} d_{++} + T_{--} d_{--} \quad (4)$$

Lattice sums S_{ij} and T_{ij} have been taken from Tosi¹⁰ and vdw co-efficients c_{ij} and d_{ij} are taken from Shankar, Singh and Agarwal¹¹.

The last term Φ_{SR} on the R.H.S. of the eq. (1) is expressed as

$$\Phi_{SR} = S/r^m \exp(-\lambda r^n) \quad (5)$$

where S and λ are potential parameters evaluated by applying the following crystal stability conditions :

$$\Phi'(r_0) = 0 \\ \text{and } \Phi''(r_0) = 9kr_0/\beta \quad (6)$$

where k = crystals structure constant and β = isothermal compressibility.

In the above equations r_0 is the equilibrium interionic separation in the lattice and the primes denote derivatives with respect to r .

The application of the above conditions to the potentials function yields the expression for the potential parameters :

$$S = \frac{r^m [Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8]}{\exp(-\lambda r^n) (m + n\lambda r^n)} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\lambda = \frac{X + n - 2m - 1 + [(X + n - 2m - 1)^2 - \{4m(M + 1)\} - X]^{1/2}}{r^n 2n} \quad (8)$$

where

$$X = \frac{9kr_0^3 + 2Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 42C/r_0^6 + 72D/r_0^8}{Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8} \quad (9)$$

where

$z_1 = z_2 = 1$ for heavy metal halide crystals

and $m = 0, n = 1$ for BM model,

$m = 1, n = 1$ Hellmann model,

$m = 2, n = 1$ for Varshini-Shukla model,

$m = 2, n = 3/2$ for Ali-Hasan model.

The last term Φ_{SR} of the eq. (1) is the short-range overlap repulsive energy dominant in diatomic crystals. The short-range repulsive potential perturbs the spherically symmetric closed shell of an ion in a lattice as the ions are brought closer so that outer electron shells begin to overlap. An additional characteristic repulsive force becomes operative resulting from the overlapping of the ions. This repulsive force opposes the Coulombian attractive force operating between the positive and the negative ions and causes them to come to equilibrium at finite value of the interionic distance (r_0). This repulsive force in an ion becomes dominant at a very short distance, so it is known as short-range repulsive potential (SSRP). The exact form of SSRP in literature is still lacking.

Cohesive energy :

The cohesive energy W per mole is related to the interaction potential energy function $\Phi(r)$ by

$$W = -N \Phi(r) \quad (10)$$

where N is Avogadro's number.

Atomization energy :

The atomization energy of diatomic crystals is of much

interest since it gives a better idea of the stability of the crystals than the cohesive energy. Only a few experimental and theoretical attempts have been made to estimate E_a for some of these crystals. The values of E_a for a particular ionic crystal AB may also be computed from the interaction potential energy function by the relation,

$$E_a = W + E - I \quad (11)$$

where E is the electron affinity and I is the ionisation energy of ions. In the present calculation the values of I have been taken from Massey¹² and those of E from Ladd and Lee¹³.

Force constant (f), IR absorption frequency (ν_0) and Debye temperature (θ_D) :

The force constant¹⁴ f is defined as

$$f = 1/3 [\Psi''(r_0) + 2r_0^{-1} \Psi'(r_0)] \quad (12)$$

where $\Psi(r)$ is the non-Coulombic part of $\Phi(r)$ and r_0 is the equilibrium interionic distance in crystalline states. Its values are taken from Sinha *et al.*¹⁵.

The IR absorption frequency (ν_0) is given by

$$\nu_0 = 1/2\pi(fm)^{1/2}$$

where m is the reduced mass.

Once the value of ν_0 is obtained, the Debye temperature θ_D can be calculated from the relation,

$$\theta_D = h\nu_0/k$$

where h is the Planck's constant and k is the Boltzmann constant.

Grüneisen parameter, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter :

The Grüneisen parameter γ is the first significant measure of the anharmonicity in solids. It is related to $\Phi(r)$ by

$$\gamma = -1/6r_0 \Phi'''(r_0)/\Phi''(r_0) \quad (13)$$

where $\Phi''(r)$ and $\Phi'''(r)$ refer to the second and third derivatives of $\Phi(r)$.

The Anderson-Grüneisen parameter :

Anderson-Grüneisen parameters δ have been computed using Chang's expression¹⁶ connecting γ and δ which was derived on the basis of Dugdale and MacDonald formula¹⁷ relating γ to the change of compressibility with volume.

The values of the Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 have been computed for the potential $\Phi(r)$ using the relation,

$$C_1 = 1 - (r_0^3 \beta/27V) \Phi'''(r_0) \quad (14)$$

where β is the compressibility of the crystals and V is the volume of the unit cell.

Second Grüneisen parameter :

The first order volume dependence of the Grüneisen parameter commonly known as the second Grüneisen parameter is fundamental to the study of many basic phenomena in solids. It is an additional measure of the anharmonicity in solids. γ and q can be used to make predictions of a variety of physical properties such as the equation of state of a material and are related to thermodynamic properties. These are also important in the study of thermo-elastic properties in terms of shock-waves. The latter property is especially relevant to the study of the geophysics of the earth.

In general, the Grüneisen parameter is a function of both temperature and volume. The temperature of Grüneisen parameter for a large number of diatomic crystals can be fairly determined either experimentally or theoretically. However, the explicit dependence of Grüneisen parameter on volume is not known accurately. Davies and Parker¹⁸ were the first to define second Grüneisen parameter q as

$$q = [\delta \ln \gamma / \delta \ln \gamma]_T \quad (15)$$

Basset *et al.*¹⁹ proposed an expression for q using thermodynamic relations.

In this communication an attempt has been made to calculate q for heavy metal halide crystals using Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Varshini-Shukla forms of interaction models within the frame work of Dugdale and MacDonald theory (DM).

Grüneisen parameter (γ) based on DM theory valid at all pressures may be expressed as

$$\gamma = 1 - V/2[(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P / \partial V^2) / (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)]^{-1} \quad (16)$$

The second Grüneisen parameter (q) derived from eq. (1) is written as

$$q = -V/2\gamma[(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P / \partial V^2) / (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)]^{-1} + (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V) / (\partial^3 P / \partial V^3 - 10V^2 \partial P / \partial V + 20PV^3) - V(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P / \partial V^2) / (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^2 - (\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 + 2/3V \partial P / \partial V - 2/3 PV^2) \quad (17)$$

Hildebrand equation of state²⁰ can be used to express γ and q in terms of derivatives of potential energy function.

For crystals with NaCl-structure

$$P = -\partial\Phi/\partial V = -1/6 r^2 \Phi' (r) \quad (18)$$

$$\partial P / \partial V = -1/36 r^4 [\Phi'' - 2/r \Phi' (r)] \quad (19)$$

$$\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 = -1/216 r^6 [\Phi''' - 6/r \Phi'' + 10/r^2 \Phi'] \quad (20)$$

$$\partial^3 P / \partial V^3 = -1/1296 r^8 [\Phi'''' - 12/r \Phi''' + 52/r^2 \Phi'' - 80/r^3 \Phi'] \quad (21)$$

where the primes denote the derivatives of $\Phi (r)$ with respect to interionic separation.

Equation of state of heavy metal halide crystals :

The high pressure behaviour of these crystals is investigated by determining the compression values of these crystals by using Murnaghan logarithmic equation of state expressed as

$$V/V_0 = \exp [-1/B'_0 \log (B'_0/B_0 + 1)] \quad (22)$$

where B_0 and B'_0 are isothermal bulk modulus and its pressure derivatives, both referred to zero pressure. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals have been shown in Figs. 1-3.

Results and discussion

The latest information on heavy metal halide crystals is far from complete but this work tries to add a little to the knowledge of these crystals by predicting several crystalline state properties such as cohesive energy (W), atomization energy (E_a), force constant, IR absorption frequency (ν_0), Debye temperature, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and second Grüneisen parameter (q) respectively.

Born-Mayer (BM), Hellmann (HM), Varshini-Shukla (VS) and Ali-Hasan forms of short-range repulsive potential have been used to compute W and E_a of heavy metal halide crystals and their values are listed in Table 1. It is found that the cohesive energy and atomization energy decrease from AgF to CuI for all the models. The present values of E_a compare well with the experimental values. It is observed that the inclusion of van der Waals terms improved the results expectedly and had given the better agreement as this match was missing in earlier calculation.

Table 2 lists the calculated values of f , ν_0 and θ_D and no comparison can be had for the agreement between the theoretical and experimental values as the experimental values are not available in the literature. The present calculation shows that van der Waals energy is important for heavier crystals. It is observed that the four models give almost identical results of f , ν_0 and θ_D .

The calculated values of γ , δ , C_1 and q have been listed in Table 3. There is no experimental data to draw comparison. But the present results indicate that γ depends upon the specific volume.

We have investigated the high pressure behaviour of these crystals by determining the compression values for

Table 1. Cohesive energy (W ; kJ mol^{-1}) and atomization energy (E_a ; kJ mol^{-1}) of heavy metal halides for Born-Mayer (BM), Hellmann (Hell), Varshini-Shukla (VS) and Ali-Hasan (AH) interaction models

Crystals	W (BM)	W (Hell)	W (VS)	W (AH)	W Expt. ²¹⁻²³	E_a (BM)	E_a (Hell)	E_a (VS)	E_a (AH)	E_a Expt. values
AgF	940.07	938.89	937.67	943.6	910.9	536.67	535.49	534.77	539.66	569.0
AgCl	838.70	837.22	835.68	841.92	849.4	461.3	459.82	458.28	464.52	535.6
AgBr	808.86	807.45	805.99	811.97	824.3	373.56	372.15	370.69	376.67	497.9
AgI	778.98	777.48	775.93	782.17	882.6	558.18	356.68	355.13	361.37	456.1
TlCl	687.82	685.74	683.56	690.86	698.7	451.82	449.74	447.56	454.86	506.3
TlBr	670.76	668.85	668.83	673.77	689.7	376.86	374.95	372.93	379.87	468.6
TlI	665.03	663.88	662.70	667.77	672.8	385.63	384.48	383.3	388.37	410.0
CuCl	935.49	931.16	926.59	941.32	928.4	543.39	539.06	534.49	599.22	598.3
CuBr	892.87	888.83	884.56	898.45	903.7	442.87	438.83	434.56	448.45	556.5
CuI	871.19	868.45	885.58	876.38	892.38	435.69	432.95	430.08	440.88	514.6

Fig. 1

Fig. 3

Figs. 1, 2 & 3 : Compression V/V_0 vs pressure P (Kbar) curves for heavy metal halide based on present interionic potential models.

Fig. 2

Table 2. Calculated properties of heavy metal halide crystals
Force constant f , IR absorption frequency ν_0 and
Debye temperature θ_D

Crystals	$f \times 10^4 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$	$\nu \times 10^{12} \text{ Hz}$	θ_D (K)
AgF	10.32	9.84	472.56
AgCl	6.94	6.31	303.15
AgBr	6.30	4.53	217.65
AgI	6.31	4.06	194.89
TlCl	3.14	3.99	191.53
TlBr	3.00	2.80	134.45
TlI	3.65	2.65	127.44
CuCl	8.80	7.66	367.62
CuBr	7.76	5.79	278.10
CuI	8.62	5.57	267.41

Table 3. Values of Grüneisen parameter (γ , dimensionless), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ , dimensionless), Molewyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and second Grüneisen parameter (q , dimensionless)

Crystals	Grüneisen parameter (γ , dimensionless)				Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ , dimensionless)				Molewyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and second Grüneisen parameter (q , dimensionless)						
	γ (BM)	γ (Hell)	γ (VS)	γ (AH)	δ (BM)	δ (Hell)	δ (VS)	δ (AH)	C_1 (BM)	C_1 (Hell)	C_1 (VS)	C_1 (AH)	q (BM)	q (Hell)	q (AH)
AgF	2.27	2.29	2.32	2.21	4.53	4.59	4.64	4.41	5.53	5.59	5.64	5.41	0.94	0.90	0.88
AgCl	2.14	2.18	2.21	2.08	4.29	4.85	4.42	4.16	5.29	5.35	5.42	5.16	0.96	0.91	0.87
AgBr	2.17	2.20	2.23	2.10	4.33	4.40	4.46	4.21	5.33	5.40	5.46	5.20	0.96	0.92	0.87
AgI	2.13	2.17	2.20	2.07	4.26	4.33	4.40	4.14	5.26	5.33	5.40	5.14	0.86	0.80	0.75
TlCl	1.80	1.85	1.90	1.75	3.61	3.70	3.79	3.50	4.61	4.70	4.79	4.50	1.22	1.14	1.07
TlBr	1.86	1.90	1.95	1.80	3.72	3.81	3.89	3.61	4.72	4.81	4.89	4.61	1.21	1.14	1.07
TlI	2.27	2.30	2.34	2.20	4.54	4.61	4.67	4.41	5.54	5.61	5.67	5.41	1.17	1.12	1.08
CuCl	1.69	1.76	1.82	1.63	3.38	3.51	3.64	3.25	4.38	4.51	4.64	4.25	0.98	0.84	0.73
CuBr	1.72	1.78	1.84	1.65	3.43	3.56	3.69	3.30	4.43	4.56	4.69	4.30	0.98	0.84	0.73
CuI	2.066	2.11	2.16	1.99	4.12	4.22	4.31	3.98	5.12	5.22	5.31	4.98	0.98	0.90	0.83

these crystals with the help of Murraghan logarithmic equation of state. The equation works well up to very high pressure. The compression curves are given in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. The experimental data for the compressions of heavy metal halide crystals are not available in the literature and hence it is not possible to draw experimental curves for these crystals.

Conclusion :

Born-Mayer, Hellmann, Varshini-Shukla and Ali-Hasan forms of interaction potential have been applied to get different crystalline state properties of heavy metal halide crystals. The latter two models give encouraging results and may prove useful for further computation of the properties of such crystals.

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